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Review Article

Formulation And Evaluation of Herbal Eye Patches for Under-Eye Hydration and Dark Circle Reduction

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ABSTRACT

The human emotions are complex part of every individual. The everyday life is much more stress full and in the today's era due to the lack of career opportunities, relationships, rapidly changing lifestyle and many more reasons. The most of the persons have psychiatry disorder like depression, anxiety, discomfort. These are the disorders which are characterized with the human emotions regulation. The hormones are the main components of the body which induce the emotions and change the mood of every individual person. The hormones that characterize the emotions are cortisol, serotonin, dopamine, testosterone, oxytocin, estradiol, adrenaline etc. The treatment of this hormonal or emotional disorder includes medicated narcotic preparation which are injurious or have measure side effect and psychological sessions which is practically expensive and cannot be afforded by everyone. The natural herbs used in day to day life can be used to treat or regulate the hormonal changes. The drugs like Bacopa moniieri, rhodeola rosea, gotu kola, turmeric, ashwagandha, peppermint etc can be used to reduce psychological disorder like anxiety, depression. In these review we are going to discuss the therapeutic benefits of herbs in the treatment of neurological disorder as a emotion hormonal regulators.

INTRODUCTION

Hormones are the chemical messenger in living organism which responsible for life processes like energy production, metabolism, in the body. The hormones are released from the glands. The glands are of two types which release the hormones which

are endocrine and exocrine. The glands are responsible for the neurological stimuli-es. The hormones are the chemicals which generate the human emotions. The hormones are not only responsible for the emotions but also held the responsibility of functioning of neurological responses. The hormone which measurely

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responsible for the controlling the emotions are cortisol which also known as the stress hormone, serotonin which also known as the happy hormone or feel good hormone, dopamine which causes the excitation properties which can be harmful for the body if it released in high quantity also plays measure role in the positive and negative feedback mechanism, oxytocin is emotion hormone which have main responsibility to decrease labour pain in labour but also responsible love between two opposite gender individual. It is also called as the love hormone. Adrenaline, nor adrenaline, vasopressin, gonads also affect the human emotions and cause affect on neurological function of the body. (1; 2) Stress is responsible for the many disorder because it cause the measure neuro degenerative properties. The stress causes many psychological disorder which disturbs the chronological functions of body. The everyday life is consist of various activities like work,studying ,relationship and much more. The things are crucial part of every individual life . but due to the

unhealthy lifestyle , heavy work load , tension about career , effect of study preparation ,failure in relationship , unhealthy diet etc.. person may get stress and constant hammering of this stress load develop into the psychological disorder like depression , anxiety ,panic attack, alzheimers disease etc.the treatment for this consist of many narcotic drugs which comes under schedule X drugs. The schedule x drugs are generally specified as the addictive drugs so they are both habit forming and harmful to body there are several methods which used to control the stress are physiological methods like yoga , exercise , book reading , ounce of entertainment etc. (3) We are going to discuss about the natural herbs that have tendency to reduce depression, anxiety ,alzheimers disease. Not only these but they can be also to use as the nootropics the drugs that increase the memory concentration and also give the natural relief of freshness. They have lesser side effect than the synthetic drugs used. The herbs that we are going to discuss as follows:

Table 1: Herbs Used to Treat Psychological Treatment

Herbs	Biological Name	Family	Uses
Brahmi	<i>Bacopa Monieri</i>	Plantaginaceae	Memory Improvement, Insomnia ,Epilepsy, Anxiolytic
Gotu Kola	<i>Centella Asiatica</i>	Apiaceae	Improve Mental Clarity ,Leprosy ,Heal Wounds
Golden Root	<i>Rhodeola Rosea</i>	Crassulaceae	Increase Mental Capacity , Resist Effect Of Stress, Anxiolytic
Rosemary	<i>Rosmarinus Officinalis L.</i>	Lamiaceae	Nervous Agitation , Improvement In Memory , Depression , Epilepsy
Lion's Mane	<i>Hericum Erinaceus</i>	Hariciaceae	Improve Nerve Development
Lemon Balm	<i>Melissa Officinalis L.</i>	Lamiaceae	Reduce Stress And Anxiety , Improve Appetite ,Promote Sleep
Ashwagandha	<i>Withania Somnifera</i>	Solanaceae	Used In Treatment Of Stress And Anxiety , Hypoglycemic
Chamomile	<i>Matricaria Chamomilla</i>	Asteraceae	Used As Neuropsychiatric ,Depression Treatment
Ginkgo	<i>Ginkgo Biloba</i>	Ginkgoceae	Dementia , Anxiolytic , To Treat Various Allergies
Asian Ginseng	<i>Panax Ginseng</i>	Araliaceae	Improve Thinking , Relieve Stress , Increase Reaction Time

● **Psychological diseases: (2)**

◆ **Depression:** the depression is a psychological disease which cause due to the consistent stress about any situation. The depression is result of hormonal changes in hormones like cortisol , dopamine , nor adrenaline , serotonin etc. The long term depression may cause changes in chronopharmacology of human body and give enhancement to other diseases.

◆ **Anxiety :**the anxiety is a disorder which result in constant fear , excessive stress and change psychological behavior. The anxiety is cause due to the increase in hormones like cortisol , epinephrine etc

◆ **Post-traumatic stress disorder:** there are a lot of types of trauma the mental trauma is caused due to the stress and hormonal imbalance which may results in serious cell injury.

◆ **Alzheimers disease :** the alzheimers disease is a disease which cause memory loss which can cause due to genetic defect or serious brain injury. It is a type of dementia.

◆ **Eating problems:** the sudden hormonal imbalance may cause change in apetite which further develop into the loss of weight and energy.

◆ **Schizophrenia:** these is the disease which resist the persons ability to think and clearly behave. It is due to the imbalance of the hormons like serotonin, dopamine, and glutamate.

● **Herbs Used in The Psychological Disorder**

A. **Bacopa Moniieri:**

Fig 1: Bacopa Moniieri

Bacopa moniieri is a herbal plant from the family planataginaceae. These plant is used from ancient times by our ansisters in the treatment of various diseases like cancer, diabetes, Parkinson and Alzheimer's disease.it is especially used in the treatment of the neurodegenerative diseases. It is also used in the cure of diseases like anxiety, depression etc.the Bacopa moniieri is a herbal plant which have alot of branches , oblong leaves and the purple flowers. The Bacopa moniieri have main chemical constituents are bacosides, bacopasides, bacopasaponin, cucurbitacin etc. (4)

Fig 2: Chemical constituents of *bacopa monieri* (5)

➤ ***B. monieri* in treatment of psychological disorder**

1. Parkinson is a disease that destroys the nerve cells which are present in the substantia nigra. As per the biological study performed in the *Caenorhabditis elegans* model with the extract of bacosides from *Bacopa monieri*. The bacosides reduce the aggregation of alpha synuclein which successfully stopped the degeneration of dopamine nerve cells.

2. In the treatment of Alzheimer's disease the active constituent present in *B. monieri* (brahmi) suppresses beta amyloid deposition in the brain. Which increases the memory enhancing properties. The herb increases the recovery and retention of nerve cells.

3. According to biological study performed with amyloid peptide which eventually increases the acetylcholine esterase (AChE) and that caused the increase in stress stimulation. The animal treated with the brahmi normalized the AChE level, reduced the neural death and decreased or controlled the stress condition.

4. As per the clinical studies performed with BME to determine the cognitive performance, 46 people were examined with the placebo effect and 320 mg of BME for about 12 weeks. In the result, the people with drug have significant increase in

learning capabilities, information processing and have less stress as compared to people with placebo. (6)

A. *Centella Asiatica*: -

Fig 3: *Centella Asiatica*

Centella asiatica is a medicinal herbal plant which has various therapeutic benefits. It is also known as the native name gotu kola and belongs to the family Apiaceae. The stem of the gotu kola is green in color. The flowers are white and in color some also appear to be crimson. The *Centella asiatica* has many more pharmacological activities in dermatological disease, endocrine, cardiovascular, respiratory and neurological diseases. The *C. asiatica* mainly contains pentacyclic triterpenoids and trisaccharide derivatives which include brahmoside, Asiatic acid, brahmic acid, centelloside, etc. (7)

Fig 4: Chemical constituents of *Centella asiatica* (8)

➤ **Psychological benefits of C. asiatica**

1. Antidepressant activity is shown due to the triterpenoids present in C.A. The pharmacological study is performed in the swimming mice with immobility activity and imbalance of amino acid. The imipramine and triterpenes decreased the immobility and imbalance of amino acid showing potent antidepressant activity.

2. C.A also increases the attention and concentration of individual. A study performed on the rats shows an increase in the cognitive function and antioxidant properties. The dose administered is (100, 200 and 300 mg/kg for 21 days) was tested in intracerebroventricular (i.c.v) streptozotocin (STZ)-induced cognitive and stress caused by oxygen. The normal rat which are given with the dose of CA showed the dose dependent increase in cognitive performance in elevated plus maze paradigms.

3. A clinical study was performed in which 28 participants (<61 year of age) received either CA or placebo in order to study the cognitive properties of CA with a dose of (250, 500, or 750 mg daily). After the time span of 2 months cognitive

properties (with event related potential and the computerized assessment battery test) and mood (using Bond-ladder visual analogue) was determined. The most improvement in cognitive function was shown by 750 mg dose of CA extract.

4. A clinical study also performed to test anxiolytic properties of CA. A study performed in 60 elderly subjects of 65 and above, using a diagnostic tool like a diagnostic tool like mini mental state examination scoring (MMSE). The study showed significant improvement after the taking dose of CA for 6 months in elderly with mild cognitive impairment (MCI) with a dose of 500mg twice a day. (8) (7)

B. Rosemarinus Officinalis: -

Fig 5: *Rosemarinus Officinalis*

Rosemarinus officinalis L. is a herb that belongs to family lamiaceae. It also has a common name as rosemary. The betulinic acid, oleanolic acid, micromeric, rosmanol, epirosmanol and luteolin are the main chemical constituents present

in rosemary. The extract of rosemary shows various therapeutic benefits such as antioxidant, antidepressants, in treatment of epilepsy, preservation of food etc. (9)

Fig 6: Chemical constituents of *Rosemarinus officinalis*

➤ **R.officinalis in psychological disorder:**

1. Depression is a major psychological disorder. The clinical studies performed on the crude hydro-alcoholic extract of rosemary showed potent antidepressant activity. The hydro-alcoholic extract of leaves of rosemary (100mg/kg) was given for 14 days and revealed antidepressant activity in mice. The activity depends on interaction with receptors like noradrenergic (alpha 1-receptor), serotonergic (5-HT_{1A}, 5HT_{2A} and 5HT_{3A} receptors), dopaminergic (D₁ and D₂ receptors). The study reported that the extract is similar to fluoxetine (10 mg/kg, PO), although the study can't determine which constituent is responsible for the activity. That is the drawback of using crude extract.

2. According to survey the number of elderly adults above 65 years old will double by the year 2030, so as the concern it is important to enhance

cognitiveness of people. The herbs are probably solving this concern so many herbs are getting tested for improvement in cognitive activity. Rosemary has potent antioxidant activity and oxidative stress is mainly responsible for decline in cognitiveness. The rosemary extract contains 60 or 10% carnosic acid and 5% of rosmarinic acid. The extract was tested on mice for 90 days which shows memory improvement in mice.

3. The diseases of CNS like anxiety, depression, Parkinson, Alzheimer's etc are dangerous and rapidly increasing. *R.officinalis* is tested gradually in recent years for treatment. Over the studies regarding depression there is a decrease in neurotransmitters like dopamine, nor epinephrine, serotonin, acetylcholine and gene expression in mice brain like TH, PC, and MAPK phosphate (MKP-1). These studies contribute to understanding the antidepressant activities of *R.officinalis*.

Hericium Erinaceus:-

Fig 7: Hericium Erinaceus

Hericium erinaceus is mushroom herb belong to family hericiaceae. It is also commonly known as lion's Mane. It known to be potent neuro protective agent. which reduce oxidative stress , stimulate nerve growth factor release, reduce stress and anxiety. It have main active constituent such as terpenoids, cerebrosides, phenols , sterols , hericenones, and erinacine etc. It have higher cognitive function due to have high neuro regeneration properties. (10)

Erinacin A

Fig 8: Chemical constituents of *Hericium erinaceus*

➤ **Psychological properties of hericium erinaceus:-**

1. The first cognitive function was studied in wild mice (in vivo). The oral supplementation of *H. erinaceus* significantly improved recognition memory of mice. By the behaviour test and increased spontaneous and induced synaptic activity in the CA3 synapse in mice in the hippocampal section. Which concluded the cognitive activity of *H. erinaceus*.

2. Oxidative stress is a main reason of memory loss which leads to Major diseases like Alzheimer's and Parkinson disease. Research has demonstrated that hot water extract from HE have high radical scavenging properties which inhibit lipid peroxidation. previous studies conducted on MPTP-induced mouse model showed that HE extract countered oxidative stress. The studies concluded that HE reduced nitrotyrosine and 4-HNE expression and restored motor function in mice. These studies showed that HE extract significantly decreased neurodegenerative activity.

3. In an mouse model of Alzheimer's disease. The HE extract administered orally increased expression of mRNA in hippocampus which restricted impairment of short term and visual recognition of memory induced by amyloid beta plaque that were observed in untreated mice. (10)

C. *Melissa Officinalis*:-

Fig 9: *Melissa Officinalis*

Melissa officinalis L. is a plant which widely used as a neuroprotective agent belongs to family Lamiaceae. It is rich in biological compounds containing mainly flavonoids, terpenoids, phenolic acids, tannins, essential oils. The main chemical composition of *M. officinalis* are volatile oils (geranial, neral, citronella and geraniol), ursolic acid, oleanolic acid, rosmarinic acid etc. The plant commonly grows in Mediterranean region, Europe and western Asia. It is also known to be lemon balm. The plant has activity like anti-inflammatory, antipain, improvement in behaviour, anxiolytic, stress reliever etc (11)

Fig 10: Chemical constituents of *M. officinalis* (11)

➤ Psychological effects of *M. officinalis*

1. In the pharmacological study the total of 60 patients are treated with the extract of *M. officinalis* or placebo in which 44 patients completed the blind type of clinical trial for 12 weeks in which significant decrease is observed in the symptoms of depression and anxiety ($p < 0.0001$ & $p = 0.04$ respectively)

2. In the pharmacological study the animals were randomly assigned to 5 groups ($n = 12/\text{group}$)

control as restraint stress (+M50,+M75,+M150) the animals are kept in cages and received 0.9% saline by gavage. The mice with restraint stress +M50,+M75,+M150 are given with doses 50, 75 and 150 mg/kg-1 day-1 of HAEMO respectively for 14 days then by performing various tests like behaviour analysis, open field test, elevated plus maze, forced swimming test, tail suspension test etc the antidepressant and anxiolytic study of MO was determined. (11)

D. *Withania Somnifera*

Fig 11: *Withania Somnifera*

In the recent years the *Withania somnifera* also known as ashwagandha, winter cherry etc used as an effective adaptogen, sedative, neuroprotective and effect on sleep disorder. It also has properties like anti-inflammatory, anti-microbial, anti-diabetic etc. Its various chemical constituents that are responsible for the therapeutic activity are alkaloids (isopelletierine, ananerin, cuseohygrine, anahygrine, etc.), steroidal lactones (withanolides, withaferins) and saponins etc (12)

Fig 12: Chemical constituents of *withania somnifera* (12)

➤ **Psychological effects of *withania somnifera*:**

1. The *withania somnifera* show promising effect in the treatment of Alzheimer's disease in which β amyloid protein in brain show neurotoxic effect and form fibrils which cause formation of free radicals and impairs the transfer of glucose in neurons which leads to cell damage or death. the hyperphosphorylated for cluster along the core of senile plaque consist of β amyloid protein. The constituent vitanon which is isolated from the roots of ashwagandha shows significant improvements in cognitive function and inhibit β amyloid, reduce pro inflammatory cytokines TNF alpha, IL-1 β , IL 6 and MCP 1, nitric oxide etc which show effect in the treatment of Alzheimer's disease.

2. The *withania somnifera* also used in the treatment of Parkinson disease in which a study is conducted on rats with 6- hydroxy dopamine induced Parkinson disease. The rat are treated with the dose of *withania somnifera* as 100,200, and 300 mg/kgbody weight for 3 weeks. In which the extract reduced the rate of lipoperoxidation and increased the conc of glutathione which increase D2 receptors binding activity. The extract with conc increase the biochemical parameters which leads to anti Parkinson activity. (12)

Fig13: *Matricaria Chamomilla L.*

Chamomile (*Matricaria chamomila* L.) is a medicinal plant used for various therapeutic benefits belong to family asteraceae. The chamomile is highly favoured as folk and traditional remedy medicine. The chamomile is used for various benefits like analgesic, antiallergic, anticancer, anxiolytic, hepatoprotective, immunomodulatory etc there are about 120 chemical constituents have identified and used as medicines including terpenoids, flavonoids etc the major chemical constituents are Iso butyl angelate, farnesene, farnesol, chamazulene etc (13)

Fig 14 : Chemical constituents of *matricaria chamomila* L (13)

➤ **Psychological properties of *Matricaria chamomila* L.**

1. The anxiolytic study was conducted on the chamomile by double blind, placebo controlled trial was evaluated. The 61 patient of generalized anxiety disorder (GAD) was treated 28 (with extract) 29 (with placebo) for 8 weeks. As a result extract treated patients showed significant reductions in Hamilton anxiety rating (HAM-A) score of chamomile group is (P=0.047) which shows anxiolytic action of chamomile.

2. A study investigates the neuroprotective effects of German chamomile (*Matricaria recutita* L.) against oxidative stress induced by aluminium fluoride (AlF₄⁻) in rats. Sprague-Dawley rats were divided into groups, with some receiving varying doses of German chamomile methanol extract (GCME) alongside AlF₄⁻, while others served as controls. After 10 days of treatment and 7 days of AlF₄⁻ administration, the study measured levels of oxidative stress markers and conducted histopathological evaluations. Results indicated that GCME significantly reduced lipid peroxidation and enhanced levels of antioxidant enzymes (superoxide dismutase, catalase, glutathione, and total thiols) in a dose-dependent manner compared to the negative control. Histopathological analyses also confirmed the neuroprotective effects of German chamomile

against oxidative brain damage, marking the first evidence of its protective activity in this context. (13)

CONCLUSION: -

Human emotions are intricately linked to hormonal regulation, with stressors in modern life often leading to psychiatric disorders like depression and anxiety. Traditional treatments often involve medications with significant side effects and costly psychological therapies. This review highlights the therapeutic potential of natural herbs in regulating emotional and hormonal imbalances. Key herbs, such as *Bacopa monnieri*, Gotu Kola, and Ashwagandha, have demonstrated efficacy in improving mental clarity, reducing anxiety, and enhancing memory. Other herbs like Rosemary and Lion's Mane exhibit neuroprotective properties, potentially aiding in conditions like Alzheimer's and Parkinson's diseases. Studies indicate that these herbal remedies can offer a natural and less harmful alternative to synthetic drugs, providing psychological relief and cognitive enhancement with minimal side effects. Thus, integrating these herbs into treatment protocols could be a valuable strategy for addressing emotional and psychological disorders.

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